

Scheme 1

1-aryldihydro-5-(arylamino)thiazole-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1*H*,5*H*)-pyrimidinediones (**4a-k**) using arylamines of formaldehyde and to 1-aryldihydro-5-(substituted-arylmethylene)-1-aryl-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1*H*,5*H*)-pyrimidinediones (**5a-f**) using arylaldehyde (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian A-90D spectrometer and mass spectra on a JMSD 300 instrument fitted with JMS 2000 data system at 70 eV.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole (1): It was synthesised according to the reported method⁵.

N-Aryl-N'-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)thioureas (2): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) in benzene (30 ml) and aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 8 h. The

5-[[[Arylamino]methyl]/[Arylmethylene]]dihydro-1-aryl-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1*H*,5*H*)pyrimidinediones and their Antiparkinsonian Activity

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THE central nervous system activity of pyrimidine derivatives is well documented^{1,2}. The pharmacological effect of pyrimidinediones against parkinsonism has been a matter of studies and earlier efforts from our laboratory have evoked some promising results³. Since different substitution at 1, 3 and 5-positions of pyrimidine ring have resulted in the antiparkinsonian activity of varied order⁴, we have made these positions the target for the substitution. In the present work 4-phenylthiazole, a biologically active moiety⁵ was incorporated at position-3 of the pyrimidinedione nucleus and other substitutions were made at 1 and 5-positions (Scheme 1). The resulting compounds were tested for their antiparkinsonian activity and toxicity in rats and mice. An attempt has also been made to take an insight into the structure-activity relationship.

2-Amino-4-phenyl thiazole (**1**) was synthesised by the reaction of acetophenone with thiourea. It was converted to *N*-phenyl-*N'*-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-thioureas (**2a, b**) by the reaction with aryl isothiocyanate. The thioureas on reaction with malonic acid in presence of acetyl chloride underwent intermolecular cyclisation to 1-aryldihydro-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1*H*,5*H*)-pyrimidinediones (**3a, b**). The pyrimidinediones (**3**) were converted to

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Ar	Ar'	M.p. °C	Oxotremorine (0.5 mg/kg i.p.) induced mice (Tremor index)	Reserpine (5 mg/kg i.p. induced rats)		
					Rigidity % \downarrow °	Hypokinesia % count	Catatonias (mean score)
2a	C ₆ H ₅	—	135	—	—	—	—
2b	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	—	176	—	—	—	—
3a	C ₆ H ₅	—	128	—	—	—	—
3b	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	—	189	—	—	—	—
4a	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	135	3.0±0	80	6.8	3.0±0
4b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	173	2.6±.24	90	7.2	2.6±.28
4c	C ₆ H ₅	2-Cl.4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	115	2.6±.24	100	7.5	2.25±.23 ^a
4d	C ₆ H ₅	2,5-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	84	3.0±0	100	30.5	2.0±.22 ^a
4e	C ₆ H ₅	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	170	3.0±0	90	6.8	2.8±.08
4f	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	199	3.0±0	100	18.5	1.6±.53 ^a
4g	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	85	3.0±0	80	6.8	2.7±.19
4h	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	114	3.0±0	100	6.9	2.8±.08
4i	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	2-Cl.4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	112	3.0±0	80	41.5	2.25±.23 ^a
4j	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2,5-Cl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	118	3.0±0	90	6.9	2.9±.10
4k	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	102	3.0±0	100	22.2	1.9±.30 ^a
5a	C ₆ H ₅	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	163	3.0±0	100	6.8	3.0±0
5b	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ .4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	172	3.0±.24	100	7.2	3.0±0
5c	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	145	2.4±.22 [*]	100	7.5	3.0±0
5d	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	166	3.0±0	100	7.6	3.0±0
5e	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	3-OCH ₃ .4-OH.C ₆ H ₃	172	2.6±.24	80	6.8	2.5±.15 ^a
5f	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	180	3.0±0	60	6.6	2.3±.50
Control	—	—	—	3.0±0	100	6.67	3.0±0
L-Dopa	—	—	—	2.6±.24	80	30.34	2.8±.08

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. ^aCompound P < 0.05.

solvent was then removed and the resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether : 2b ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 070 (C=S) and 3 380 cm^{-1} (NH) ; m/z 325 mol. ion peak), 165, 150, 134, 107 (base peak) and 91.

1-Aryldihydro-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1H, 5H)-pyrimidinedione (3) : To a solution of 2 (0.015 mol) in acetyl chloride (10 ml), malonic acid (0.02 mol) was added and the mixture was heated for 6 h at 40°. It was then cooled and poured into crushed ice and the resulting solid was recrystallised : 3a ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 080 (C=S), 1 680 (C=O) and 2 850 cm^{-1} (CH₂) ; δ (CDCl₃) 6.5–7.7 (10H, m, aromatic and 1H thiazole ring), 2.2–2.7 (2H, s, CH₂ pyrimidinedione ring) ; 3b m/z 393 (mol. ion peak), A⁺ at 218, B⁺ 175, C⁺ 176 (base peak), D⁺ 42, E⁺ 134, F⁺ 91, G⁺ 76, H⁺ 134, I⁺ 102, J⁺ 89, K⁺ 77 and L⁺ 58.

1-Aryldihydro-5-(arylaminoethyl)-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1H,5H)-pyrimidinediones (4) : To a solution of 3 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) were added arylamine (0.01 mol) and formaldehyde (0.015 mol). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and refluxed for another 6 h. It was then concentrated, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised : 4h ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 070 (C=S), 1 680 (C=O) and 3 360 cm^{-1} (NH) ; m/z 408 (mol. ion peak), 392, 218, 176 (base peak) and 77.

1-Aryldihydro-5-(substituted-aryl)methylene)-3-(4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl)-2-thioxo-4,6-(1H,5H)-pyrimidinedione (5) : A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol), arylaldehyde (0.01 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.015 mol) in glacial acetic acid (35 ml) was refluxed for 8 h,

then poured in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised : 5e ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 070 (C=S), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=C) ; m/z 527 (M^+) (mol. ion) 392, 135, 218, 174 and 176 (base peak).

Biological studies : Antiparkinsonian activity study was carried out in albino mice (20–30 g) and rats (100–200 g) of either sex, and tested against oxotremorine (0.5 mg/kg i.p) induced tremors⁶ and reserpine (5 mg/kg i.p) induced rigidity⁷, hypokinesia⁸ and catatonias⁹.

Acute neurological toxicity was studied according to the reported method¹⁰ and ALD₅₀ value was determined¹¹.

The results are given in Table 1.

The oxotremorine induced tremors were best antagonised by compound 5c the activity being better than L-dopa ; the compound is characterised by the presence of phenyl group at position-1 and 2-hydroxybenzylidene group at position-5 of pyrimidine ring. Compounds 4b, 4c and 5b exhibited antitremor activity comparable to L-dopa ; all these compounds have phenyl group present at position-1.

Compound 5f, having 2-methylphenyl group at position-1 and 2-hydroxybenzylidene group at position-5 of the pyrimidine nucleus reduced the reserpine induced rigidity from control value of 100 to 60% as compared to 80% by L-dopa. Compounds 4g, 4i and 5e showed antirigidity activity similar to l-dopa ; 4g, 4i and 5e have 2-methylphenyl groups at position-1.

Potent antihypokinetic activity was found in 4d and 4i. Compound 4i having 2-methylphenyl

group at position-5 via methylaminochain exhibited antihypokinetic activity better than L-dopa whereas **4d** was comparable to L-dopa.

Compounds **4c**, **4d**, **4f**, **4i**, **4k**, **5c** and **5f** exhibited antitremor activity, marked inhibition having shown by **4f** and **4k** having 2-methylphenyl group at position-1.

The results of the study show that compounds having phenyl substitution at position-1 exhibited potent antitremor activity whereas those having 2-methylphenyl group at the same position were devoid of any such activity. The presence of 2-methylphenyl group at position-1, however, appears to influence antirigidity activity as most of the compounds showing inhibition of reserpine induced rigidity have such substitution. All the active compounds have $ALD_{50} > 1000$ mg/kg.

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